

Feasibility studies for isolation of humic acid from coal of Mongchen Coalfield, Nagaland

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Abstract : Rampant coal mining are being carried out in almost all the coal bearing areas of Nagaland which degrading the environment including soil. With a view to reclaim the lands degraded by mining of coal, we find a possibilities of isolating humic acid from inferior (shaly) coal and coal wastes of Mongchen Coalfield, Nagaland. Humic acid the black gold of agriculture is a commercial term referring to combined humic and fulvic acids. They are also known to be most biochemically active materials. Humic acid are macromolecular substance of a predominantly aromatic character with an extremely complex structure. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to prepare the humic acid from the low grade coal of Monchem Coalfield by oxidation followed by alkali extraction and separation techniques. All the results reveal that humic acid can be isolated from the coal samples under study. The product was characterized by FTIR spectra, UV-Visible spectroscopy, SEM and XRD.

Keywords : Humic acid, oxidation, coal.

Introduction

Northern Mongchen coalfield is a part of the Melak-Tzurang (Jhaji-Desai) valley Coalbelt belonging to the Mongchen-Dibuia sector of Changkikong Range coalfields. Systematic geological investigation in Northern Mongchen Coalfield have been completed and drilling operation of the first bore hole with target of 120 m depth has been stated on 2008¹. The area belongs to tertiary age and tikak parbat formation of the Barails, is which is sandwiched between Tipam sandstone¹. The coal seams/bands in general trends towards NE-SW though the direction differs near contact of different formations (Tipam sandstone). Amount of dip also varies near contact ranging from 60° to nearly 90° which decreases considerably upto 30° to 23° as it goes further away from the contact zone¹. The coals of Northern Mongchen Coalfield like any other tertiary coal of the North Eastern Region have high sulphur, volatile matter and calorific value but are low in ash content. Four million tons of coals are reported. In the Mongchen Coalfield, Melak-Tzurang (Jhaji-Desai) Valley Coalbelt, Mokokchung District, Nagaland (Fig. 1). While mining coals, associated rocks and mine tailing are dumped as overburden/mine tailings anywhere near the mine mouths. This mine rejects along with the

coal particles has high sulphur contents and produce highly acidic (pH 2.0–3.0) leachates. For primary succession in such adverse environment, a minimum period of 25 to 30 years is essential for plant rejuvenation. For reclaiming such man made acidic soils, treatment of the affected soil is necessary for a forestation or other agricultural activities. Therefore, a soil conditioner for making the soil suitable for such purposes is almost necessary. Humic acid derived from coals is a new concept which can be prepared from low grade coals and can be used for all types of soils¹. Humic acid are macromolecular substance and could be used for complexation of toxic elements released during acid mine formation². With a view to reclaiming the lands degraded by mining of coal, we have to find the possibilities of manufacturing of the humic acid from the inferior (shaly) coal and coal wastes of Mongchen Coalfield.

In the present investigation, an attempt has been made to isolate humic acid from low grade coals of Mongchen Coalfield. Different methods like non-catalytic oxidation with oxygen³, oxidation using nitric acid⁴, alkaline extraction followed by acidic precipitation and membrane separation⁵, oxidation with H₂O₂ and KMnO₄⁶, method applied by International Humic Acid Substance Society

Fig. 1. Geological map of the Mongchen Coalfield (A) and sample collecting sites (B, C, D).

(IHASS) has been applied to prepare humic acid from coal. In present method, oxidations of coals are carried out using hydrogen peroxide and formic acid (to increase the oxygen functionalities)⁷ followed by alkaline extraction, acidic precipitation and separation techniques.

Experimental

Two numbers of coal samples (Coal-1 and Coal-2) from Northern Mongchen Coalfield, Nagaland was selected and crushed to below 1/8" size and ball milled to 0.211 mm sizes. The proximate, ultimate analysis of the samples studied was done by Leco TGA 701 ProximateAnalyser and Leco, CHN Analyzer respectively. Total sulphur was determined by Leco S 144DR SulfurDeterminator (accuracy ±0.02). The physico-chemical properties of the coal samples studied and yield of humic acid were summarized in Table 1.

Oxidation of coal samples :

The experiment is carried out by refluxing 100 g of each coal with 250 ml of 20% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and 44 ml of 20% formic acid (HCOOH) for 1 h at atmospheric pressure and in ice cold condition. Hydrogen per-

Table 1. Codes for samples studied

Samples	Codes
1. Shaly coal; size : 0-1.5"	Coal-1
2. Inferior coal, brownish black, size : 0-10", yellow patch found due to pyrites	Coal-2
3. Low ash NER coal	Coal-3
4. Shaly coal; size : 0-1.5"(after HCl treatment)	Coal-4
5. Humic acid (Shaly coal; size : 0-1.5")	HAS-1
6. Humic acid after HCL treatment (Shaly coal; size : 0-1.5")	HAS-2
7. Standard humic acid	HAS-3
8. Humic acid (Low ash NER coal)	HAS-4

oxide added drop by drop to the mixture of coal and formic acid for *in situ* formation of performic acid⁷. The oxidised coal samples were filtered and washed until the pH of the filtrate became neutral. The oven dried samples were kept for subsequent experiments.

Isolation of humic acid in sodium hydroxide :

Each oxidised coal sample was refluxed with dilute NaOH solution (1 N) for 6 h with continuous stirring and then it was cooled to room temperature, added distilled

water and kept for overnight. The final solution was filtered and the pH was raised to ≤ 1 , kept for overnight and filtered. The residue (humic acid) was obtained by filtration. Coal derived humic acid were dried, weighed and characterized using UV-Visible spectroscopy, FTIR, XRD and SEM analysis.

Isolation of humic acid from mineral free coal :

100 g coal samples (Coal-1) was mixed with 0.1 N 250 ml HCl solution with continuous stirring for one hour. The solution was filtered, washed and collected the residue and oven dried. Then the mineral free coal samples were further used for isolation of humic acid with the above procedure.

Isolation of humic acid from low ash coals :

An experiment was also carried out for isolation of humic acid from a low ash North Eastern Region coal (Coal-3) with the above process. The results are summarised in Table 4.

Determinations of acidity :

To determine the maturity of the coal samples and oxygen containing functional groups, total acidity of the coal and humic acid was determined by using the method developed by Gupta Schnitzer¹. Phenolic acid is obtained by difference between total acidity and carboxyl. The carboxylic acid and total acidity is determined according to the following equations :

$$\text{Carboxylic acid (mmole H + /g of Coal) = (VB2 - VB1) \times CB \times 1000/m coal} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Total acidity (mmol H +/g of Coal) = (VA1 - VA2) \times CA \times 1000/m coal} \quad (2)$$

where in eq. (1) VB1 and VB2 represent the volume (ml) of base pattern used to titrate the blank and sample, respectively, CB is the concentration of the base in (mol/L) and m is the mass of coal samples in milligrams. In eq. (2) VA1 and VA2 representing the volume in ml of standard acid solution used for the titration of the blank and sample respectively. CA is the acid concentration in mol/L and m is the mass of coal (mg) used in the titration. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Results and discussion

Isolated humic acid residue was found to be about 3.34% and 0.58% for Coal-1 and Coal-2 respectively. It

was observed that for both the coal samples studied (Coal-1 and Coal-2), the amount of humic acid yield was low. But coal sample (Coal-1) gives a considerable amount of humic acid, so further investigation was carried out for the coal sample (Coal-1). From the physico-chemical properties of the coal samples studied, Coal-2 have very less amount of carbon source (fixed carbon : 7.71%, carbon : 15.5%) for isolation of humic acid (Table 2).

After acid treatment of the sample under study (Coal-1) about 26.25% decrease in ash content and 5.39% increase in amount of humic acid residue. For low ash NER coal isolation of humic acid was found to be about 50%. The results reflect that ash content in coal is one of the important factors for isolation of humic acid from coal. It was observed that low ash content have high isolation value of humic acid (Fig. 2). It may be due to the formation of soluble metal-humic acid complexes during

Table 2. Physico-chemical characteristics of the coal samples

Sl. No.	Sample codes	Proximate analysis (%)			Ultimate analysis (%)		
		Moist	Ash	VM	FC	C	H
1.	Coal-1	7.68	19.5	34.9	38.0	54.7	4.64
2.	Coal-2	2.81	72.0	17.5	7.71	15.5	1.77
3.	Coal-3	6.32	2.99	39.8	50.9	75.6	5.81
4.	Coal-4	6.03	14.38	36.2	40.7	53.6	4.70
5.	HAS-1	58.0	2.01	28.8	16.2	38.1	6.79
6.	HAS-2	35.6	30.6	10.3	23.5	38.8	6.81
7.	HAS-4	11	3.2	44.88	40.92	68.4	5.23

Table 3. Yield of humic acid

Samples code	Yield (%)
Coal-1	3.342
Coal-2	0.58
Coal-4	5.39
Coal-3	50.0

Table 4. Determination of acidity of the coal and humic acid samples

Coal samples	Total acidity (mmol/g)	-COOH (mmol/g)	-OH (mmol/g)	COOH/OH
Coal-1	473.6	238.8	234.8	1.01
Coal-2	251.5	128.75	122.75	1.04
Coal-3	576.0	291.2	284.8	1.02
HAS-1	750.2	438.8	311.4	1.40
HAS-2	755.4	441.5	313.9	1.40
HAS-4	850.5	595.3	255.2	2.33

Fig. 2. Relation between ash content of the coal samples vs isolated humic acid.

Table 5. Major infrared absorption bands (cm^{-1}) of coal derived humic acids

Samples codes	Absorption bands (cm^{-1})	Intensity	Assignment	Functional class
HAS-1	3391.8	Broad	Hydrogen bonded OH and NH stretching	Alcoholic/phenolic
	1700.7	Medium	C=O stretching of -COOH group	Carboxylic acid
	1619.1	Medium	C=C, C=O, $\text{COO}^- \text{NH}_2$ scissoring (1-amines)	Amines/carboxylic acid
	1402.9	Weak	C-O-H bending	Carboxylic acid/derivatives
	1384.9	Weak	O-H bending in plane	Alcohols/phenols
	1191.6	Weak	C-O stretching	Alcohols/phenols
	1122.7	Strong	C-O stretching in C-O-C group	Alcohols/phenols
HAS-3	3391.7	Broad	Hydrogen bonded OH and NH stretching	Alcoholic/phenolic
	1604.3	Medium	C=O stretching of -COOH group	Carboxylic acid
	1400.6	Medium	C=C, C=O, $\text{COO}^- \text{NH}_2$ scissoring (1-amines)	Amines/carboxylic acid
	1384.8	Weak	C-O-H bending	Carboxylic acid/derivatives,
	1191.7	Weak	O-H bending in plane	Alcohols/phenols
	1136.0	Weak	C-O stretching in C-O-C group	Alcohols/phenols
HAS-2	1122.6	Strong	C-O stretching in C-O-C group	Alcohols/phenols
	3391.8	Broad	Hydrogen bonded OH and NH stretching	Alcoholic/phenolic
	1619.1	Medium	C=C, C=O, $\text{COO}^- \text{NH}_2$ scissoring (1-amines)	Amines/carboxylic acid
	1401.0	Weak	C-O-H bending	Carboxylic acid/derivatives
	1384.9	Weak	O-H bending in plane	Alcohols/phenols
	1191.0	Weak	C-O stretching	Alcohols/phenols
	1122.7	Strong	C-O stretching in C-O-C group	Alcohols/phenols

oxidation and isolation of humic acid of coal samples studied⁸.

Oxidation of coal under stated conditions resulted in increase in oxygen functionality through both hydroxyl

and carboxylic groups. The carboxylic group foremost compared to the hydroxyl group. The ratio of carboxylic group to hydroxyl group (COOH/OH) showed that carboxylic acid group were more preferentially formed

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of coal derived humic acid and standard humic acid.

Fig. 4. SEM image of coal derived humic acid.

through oxidations as the ratio increased from 1.1 to 1.4, 1.04 to 1.4 and 1.02 to 2.33 when comparing the parent coal to the extracted coal derived humic acid for Coal-1, Coal-2 and Coal-3 respectively.

In determination of the carboxylic acid content and total acidity is made by reacting coal with calcium acetate and respectively. The calcium acetate reacts only with the carboxylic groups (Fig. 8) and barium hydroxide reacts with both carboxyl groups and with the phenolic OH group (Fig. 9). The reaction of the humic acid and coal

Fig. 5. XRD spectra of coal derived humic acid.

Fig. 6. UV-Vis spectra of standard humic acid and coal derived humic acid.

Fig. 7. Hypothetical mechanism during extraction of humic acid from coal.

samples studied with calcium acetate and barium hydroxide follows the stoichiometry as shown below⁸.

Fig. 8. Complex formation between acidic groups of coal and humic acid with calcium ion.

Fig. 9. Complex formation between acidic group of coal and humic acid with barium ion.

On comparing the FTIR spectra of coal derived humic acid and standard humic acid shows similar in nature (Table 5, Fig. 3). Bands appearing in the region at 1100 to 1000 cm^{-1} have been frequently assigned to alcoholic and polysaccharide C–O groups stretching or to vibrations of a SiO_2 related impurity in humic substance. Moreover, the bands in this region may also arise from C–O stretching or an inorganic impurity.

In the UV-Vis spectra of coal derived humic acid a peak at 223.24 nm was observed due to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the aromatic groups present in humic acid. The coal derived humic acid was found to be transparent in the visible region. Similar results were obtained on recording UV-Vis spectra of standard humic acid (Fig. 6).

The XRD pattern (Fig. 5) shows the coal derived humic acid to have amorphous phase. The particle size and

shape are found not regular from SEM analysis (Fig. 4). The particle size varies from $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $130\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Conclusions

In accordance with the results that were achieved in this study, which examined the feasibility studies for isolation of humic acid from coal samples studied with different parameter, the following conclusions were drawn :

(i) Humic acid can be derived from these low rank coals. Amount of humic acid from coal and coal waste are low for the samples taken for feasibility studies for isolation of humic acid.

(ii) All analytical results show that coal-derived humic acid and standard humic acid are similar in nature.

(iii) Isolation of humic acid from coal samples studied depends upon the quality of the coal samples. The coals with low ash, high value of carbon content and oxygen containing functional groups coals give high amount of coal-derived humic acids.

The study reflects only the feasibility studies of isolation of humic acid which can be applied as soil conditioner. Depending upon the huge amount of market potential internationally and nationally, its applications in conditioning of agricultural soil, its utilizations and applications in different sectors the study have merit. However, for optimization of process parameters and scale up, further studies in the pilot scale to study details feasibility for isolation coal derived humic acids suitable for agricultural purposes is required.

Acknowledgement

The authors are very much thankful to the Director of CSIR-NEIST, Jorhat and CSIR, New Delhi for encouragement and financial support to carry out the work.

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